

Revelation 10: A Little Book with a Big Message

Trumpets were piercing the heavens and the earth – six in all – announcing and executing the judgments of God against the sins of mankind. One trumpet remained, one trumpet that would consummate the just wrath of God. But the trumpet does not sound. The seventh angel with the seventh trumpet waits as another angel steps forth. Instead of a trumpet, he holds a little book. But the size of the book belies his strength. He is majestic. When he speaks, it is like the roar of a lion, and the heavens respond with thunderous voices. He swears by the eternal God that there will be no more delay. God’s plan will be completed. Then, he offers the little book to the seer who consumes it. It is sweet to the taste, but once consumed sour in the stomach, and the seer must prophesy again.

Such is the vision that one reads in Revelation 10. It is a chapter of beauty, mystery, and challenge. Why did this vision happen instead of the seventh trumpet? Who or what is this angel? What is the meaning of the little book? Is it the same or different from the scroll that the Lamb received from God in Revelation 5? What does the angel mean when he says the mystery of God will be finished? Why must John consume the book?

This paper will answer these questions as it engages with the four primary views of Revelation: Historicist, Preterist, Futurist, and Idealist. Because the vision is an interlude between events, differences in interpretation are not prominent as theologians expound upon the various elements of the vision. Yet, there are some differences. Historicists believe that the little book is the Bible

which before the Reformation had been confined to a few inaccessible copies written in language ... incomprehensible to common Europeans. During the period immediately following the fall of the Byzantine Empire, the Bible became available (an open book) to the masses after two developments: the invention of the movable type printing press in

1436 or 1437, coupled with the making of several translations into the contemporary European languages.¹

From this point forward in Revelation, John will be shown “...in chronological sequence the events in the further development of the Reformation.”² When he consumes the book, “...he stands for the ministers of the Reformation, who are thereby charged by Christ to preach ... His gospel to many nations and languages.”³

Some Preterists see this chapter as a transition. Up to this time, Revelation has been about the fall of Jerusalem. Now, there will be no more delay. Jerusalem will fall, and John, by eating the scroll expands his prophesying to speak of the fall of Rome.⁴ Futurists see this interlude as an announcement that God’s OT prophecies of Israel’s tribulation leading to its exaltation in the Millennium are about to be fulfilled.⁵ Idealists see the passage as relevant to all historical realities. It was pertinent for the fall of Jerusalem (if an Idealist holds to a date in the 60s). It is a word of warning to the Roman empire, and it is God’s call for his people always to proclaim his word to all nations. There are various viewpoints if the little book refers only to chapter 11 or to the rest of Revelation.⁶

It is the opinion of this writer that one’s presuppositions about Revelation will determine how one interprets chapter 10. Standing alone, Revelation 10 yields little information that would

¹ Steve Gregg, *Revelation: Four Views Revised and Updated*, Thomas Nelson, Nashville, TN, 254.

² *Ibid.*, 260.

³ *Ibid.* 262, 264.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 254, 264.

⁵ *Ibid.*, 259, 261.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 259.

verify or disprove any of the four. Walvoord states, “Like chapter 7 it does not advance the narrative but presents other facts which contribute to the total prophetic scene.”⁷

The emphasis of this paper will be on the major elements of the vision. It will expound the words of Revelation 10 in three sections:

- 10:1-4 – The Angel and the Book
- 10:5-7 – The Angel’s Sworn Testimony
- 10:8-11 – The Angel Offers the Book for John to Consume

Once the passage is explained, the reader will see that the Idealist interpretation – that Revelation, while it was a specific word for God’s people in the first century (whether in the 60s or the 90s), always holds a vital lesson for God’s people in all places.

10:1-4 – The Angel and the Book

Then I saw another mighty angel coming down from heaven. He was robed in a cloud, with a rainbow above his head; his face was like the sun, and his legs were like fiery pillars. ²He was holding a little scroll, which lay open in his hand. He planted his right foot on the sea and his left foot on the land, ³and he gave a loud shout like the roar of a lion. When he shouted, the voices of the seven thunders spoke. ⁴And when the seven thunders spoke, I was about to write; but I heard a voice from heaven say, “Seal up what the seven thunders have said and do not write it down.”

Who is the mighty angel? Walvoord believes that the description of him as “another” was meant to keep the reader from identifying him as the sixth angel in 9:13 or the seventh in 11:15.⁸ The fact that he is called *another* mighty angel reminds the reader of the mighty angel in chapter 5 who asked who was worthy to open the book in the hand of God. These are the only places where angels are described in Revelation in this way, and they both have to do with books.

Beale believes, however, that this may be more than an angel. He believes it may be a vision of Christ as the Angel of the Lord. He points to the following descriptors. This angel

⁷ John Walvoord, *The Revelation of Jesus Christ*, Moody, Chicago, IL, 169.

⁸ Walvoord, 169.

comes with clouds which are an indication of God's Shekinah presence. He has *the* rainbow upon his head. The only other place this rainbow is mentioned is in association with God's throne in 4:3. His face and legs are described like Christ's in Revelation 1, and he roars like a lion causing one to think of the Lion of Judah who has overcome.⁹ The second section of this chapter shows the angel to be swearing by God, an action which God himself does on numerous occasions in the OT.¹⁰

Holwerda advocates an OT background for both Revelation 5 and 10; the coronation of King Joash in 2 Kings 11:12-19 and 2 Chronicles 23:11-20.

The covenant book given to the king signified not only his right to rule but also how he should rule under God as the Great King... (and) the sealed scroll transferred into Christ's hands symbolizes that Christ has become the end time ruler, the world's sovereign, God's coregent who carries out God's will and his plan for history.¹¹

These arguments seem persuasive, but Ryrie counters that "Similar characteristics are ascribed to a man (clearly an angelic being) in Daniel 10:5 ff. Furthermore, the archangel Michael's name means 'who is like God,' which would make these characteristics not unexpected."¹² Ryrie's simple observations should lead one to identify the angel as an angel and not Christ and to focus on the angel's mission.

The mission is about the little book. Beale identifies its meaning. "The scroll in 10 is the same as the meaning in 5. Christ is sovereign over all. He inaugurates the kingdom and will consummate it."¹³ But while no one would disagree with such an interpretation, various opinions

⁹ G.K. Beale, *The Book of Revelation*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 522-525.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 537. See Gen 22:16; Exod 32:13; Isa 45:43; Jer 49:13; Ezek 20:5; Amos 6:8; and Heb 6:13.

¹¹ David E. Holwerda, "The Church and the Little Scroll," *Calvin Theological Journal*, 34 No 1, April 1999, 152

¹² Charles Caldwell Ryrie, *Revelation*, Moody, Chicago, IL, 67.

¹³ Beale, 527-28.

persist if the books in 10 and 5 are the same. The issue focuses on the Greek words – *biblion* (book) and *biblardion* (little book). The latter word is the diminutive form of the former word. Bauckham and Baynes come to different conclusions.

Bauckham believes that the Greek of the first century used these words interchangeably, and Revelation bears this out. While Revelation 5 used *biblion* exclusively, chapter 10 used *biblaridion* in verses 2, 9-10, and *biblion* in verse 8. The strong angel in both passages points to it being the same book which was at one time sealed but now opened¹⁴ by the Lamb.¹⁵

Baynes disagrees. He points to the works of Origen and Oecumenius. In their commentaries on Revelation, they clearly distinguish between the two. The little book of 10 is different from the sealed book of Revelation 5. A *biblaridion* is not a *biblion*. It must be small enough to eat.¹⁶ However, despite these various scholarly positions, one should note that the message of the books will be the same. This message will be examined in the third section of this paper.

The final issue of the first section is the Seven Thunders. The mighty angel, holding the opened book, cries out like a lion, and seven peals of thunder sound. John listens to them all. He starts to write, and then, uncharacteristic for the book of Revelation which is to unseal meaning, the angel tells John to seal up and not write what the thunders said. Why? Metzger points to Paul's experience of being caught up in the third heaven and hearing things that are unlawful for

¹⁴ Ryrie, 66. He indicates that the Greek is a perfect passive. By the time one gets to chapter 10, the closed book of 5 has been opened.

¹⁵ Richard Bauckham, *The Theology of the Book of Revelation*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1993, 80-81.

¹⁶ Leslie Baynes, "Revelation 5:1 and 10:2a, 8-10 in the Earliest Greek Tradition: A Response to Richard Bauckham," *Journal of Biblical Literature*, 129, No 4, 2010, 810, 813.

him to share with others as a similar experience (2 Cor 12:4).¹⁷ Beale identifies two other possibilities; the sealing shows God's omnipotence or the judgments were canceled to hasten the end. But Beale does not believe these to be the meaning. He notes that they are *the* seven thunders indicating that they should be known to John. He points to the seven thunders of God in Psalm 29 as the key referent and concludes that John was told not to write their content because enough has been said about judgment and there was no need to be repetitive.¹⁸ Holwerda may express the point best. "If the warning judgments of the seals and the trumpets are insufficient to lead the nations to repentance, and if there is no more (visionary) time remaining for another series of similar judgments, what activity does God have in mind for the accomplishment of his mystery?"¹⁹ In other words, rather than elaborate on the judgments, God wants to get to the main point which leads to the second section of Revelation 10.

10:5-7 The Angel's Sworn Testimony

⁵ Then the angel I had seen standing on the sea and on the land raised his right hand to heaven. ⁶ And he swore by him who lives for ever and ever, who created the heavens and all that is in them, the earth and all that is in it, and the sea and all that is in it, and said, "There will be no more delay! ⁷ But in the days when the seventh angel is about to sound his trumpet, the mystery of God will be accomplished, just as he announced to his servants the prophets."

The mighty angel has one foot on the sea and another on the land. This is the second mention of the angel's posture, the first being in verse 2 and the last in verse 8. This three-fold mention of where the angel stands is significant. Walvoord, the Futurist, says that it implies "...

¹⁷ Bruce M. Metzger, *Breaking the Code: Understanding the Book of Revelation*, Abingdon, Nashville TN, 1993, 67.

¹⁸ Beale, 536.

¹⁹ Holwerda, 150.

a position of power and authority over the entire earth.”²⁰ In describing the Idealist position, Gregg says that the posture indicates it is a message for the world as the land connotes Israel and the sea connotes the Gentile world.²¹ This would coincide with the Preterist position that interprets the Greek word – *ge* – not as “the earth” but as “the land of Israel” and the sea as the gentile world.

The angel swears by the One who lives forever and who has created the sky, the land, and the sea, the three-fold dominion given to Adam in Genesis 1:28 and a refrain found in Exodus 20:11, Nehemiah 9:6, and Psalm 146:6. Beale explains that this expanded description of God “...underscores the absolute sovereignty of God in creating all things. This emphasis is intended to connect God’s universal sovereignty over the beginning of creation to Christ’s absolute rule ... over creation in the latter days of the church age and of the coming new creation.”²²

The creator who commissioned the first humans delivers a word through this angel to John that the descendants of the first humans must hear. What is this word that is accompanied by such majestic features? It is twofold. First, “there will be no more delay.” Some older translations still make their way into popular teaching; “time will be no more.” But this is not the cessation of time as humans know it. The idea is that there will be no more interval of time before the end comes.²³ Eller states that John is not like those who believe that “...human history never will involve an accounting but will simply run on forever. For John, that would make

²⁰ Walvoord, 170

²¹ Gregg, 253.

²² Beale, 538.

²³ Ryrie, 68.

history ... meaningless....”²⁴ Could this be why the seven thunders were sealed? Rather than prolonging judgment upon sinful humanity, God is saying that there will be no more delay. The end will come.

The second word from the angel is another word of completion. There will be no more delay because when the seventh angel sounds his trumpet, (and here, the reader must remember that in Revelation 8-9, the first six of the seven trumpet judgments sounded) then the mystery of God will be accomplished. What is the mystery of God? Gregg lists the various options according to the main views of Revelation. The Historicist sees the downfall of the Papacy. The Preterist views it as Jew and Gentile in one Body. As Jerusalem falls, the gospel expands in its mission to the gentiles. The Futurist sees it as God’s fulfillment of his promises to Israel in the Millennium. The Idealist position is best summed up in the words of Harrington. It is “God’s ultimate purposes in guiding creation toward the fullness of God’s reign.”²⁵

Beale probes the meaning more deeply. He sees in this vision the solution to the mystery of the sealing of the message in Daniel 12. There, a glorious being raises his hand to heaven and swears by God that the end will come. But when Daniel inquires about specifics, he is told to go his way for the words are concealed. “In contrast, John is made to understand that Daniel’s end-time prophecies concerning events preceding the consummation have actually been set in motion by Jesus’ redemptive work.”²⁶ The stage is now set for the final scene of Revelation 10.

²⁴ Vernard Eller, *The Most Revealing Book of the Bible: Making Sense of Revelation*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1975, 113.

²⁵ Daniel J. Harrington, *Revelation: The Book of the Risen Christ*, New City Press, Hyde Park NY, 1999, 89.

²⁶ Beale, 544

10:8-11 – The Angel Offers the Book for John to Consume

⁸ Then the voice that I had heard from heaven spoke to me once more: “Go, take the scroll that lies open in the hand of the angel who is standing on the sea and on the land.”
⁹ So I went to the angel and asked him to give me the little scroll. He said to me, “Take it and eat it. It will turn your stomach sour, but ‘in your mouth it will be as sweet as honey.’”¹⁰ I took the little scroll from the angel’s hand and ate it. It tasted as sweet as honey in my mouth, but when I had eaten it, my stomach turned sour. ¹¹ Then I was told, “You must prophesy again about many peoples, nations, languages and kings.”

For the second time in Revelation, a man is invited to take a book from the hand of another. The first was in Revelation 5 where the slain but overcoming Lamb took the book out of the hand of God on the throne. In Revelation 10, the suffering but overcoming servant of the Lamb is invited to take the book from the hand of the mighty angel. Beale’s insight explains the purpose of the repetitive action.

The Lamb’s taking and opening of the scroll symbolized his newly gained authority over God’s plan of judgment and redemption, which was inaugurated by his own death and resurrection. John’s similar action shows that he participates in and identifies with Jesus’ authority in executing judgment and redemption.²⁷

Christians, like Christ, have their “book,” which is also symbolic of their purpose: they are to reign ironically as Christ did by being imitators on a small scale of the great cosmic model of the cross.²⁸

And so John, with courage, for the angel is majestic and strong, walks to the angel and takes the book from his hand. Because it is small, he consumes it. The taste is as sweet as honey in his mouth, a delight to eat, but as soon as he swallows, it becomes sour in his stomach.

Commentators are nearly unanimous in their explanation of John’s sweet and sour experience. Consuming the word of God should be a sweet experience, and indeed, God’s word is likened to honey (Psalm 19:10; Psalm 119:103; see also Jer 15:16). But sometimes the word of

²⁷ Ibid., 548.

²⁸ Ibid., 549.

God has a painful message for the world and for the Church. It may entail suffering for God's people and judgment for the wicked. Ryrie has a crucial word for the Church regarding consuming God's word.

This action is also a very vivid picture of the principle that although the fact of revelation may be pleasant to the taste, the contemplation or digestion of the truth may bring heaviness. This principle ought especially to be operative in our study of prophecy. Too often when one enters into an understanding of things to come, he never gets beyond the tasting stage.²⁹

Meredith Warren argues that in the ancient world, divine revelation often involved hierophagy – the eating of otherworldly substances so that one could understand and pass on divine knowledge.³⁰ Such an amazing experience carries a burden as it did for John. He had to prophesy again about many peoples, nations, languages, and kings.³¹ It is not a glorious, simple task. It carries a price for such activity will meet with resistance and often martyrdom. But John does not flinch. He consumes the little book and does exactly what the angel says he must do. He must prophesy again. He must declare God's word, not just to Israel but to the nations.

Conclusion

The Historicist focuses on the downfall of the Papacy and the rise of the Reformation. The Preterist focuses on John's mission to Israel expanding to the nations. The Futurist focuses on an end-time message for Israel before the Millennium. But these interpretations must be

²⁹ Ryrie, 69.

³⁰ Meredith J.C. Warren, "Tasting the Little Scroll: A Sensory Analysis of Divine Interaction in Revelation 10:8-10," *Journal for the Study of the New Testament*, 2017, Vol 40 (1), 102.

³¹ There is a debate if John is told to prophesy "about" or "against." Beale's reasoning seems the weightiest. John is asked to prophesy against nations, i.e., to prophesy judgment for wickedness. He is called to continue his prophetic ministry.

imposed from prior commitments to interpret the entire book this way for Revelation 10 gives little information one way or another.

Yet, the general nature of the vision in Revelation points to John fulfilling his role from the isle of Patmos and recording the words revealed to him. In doing so, he sets a pattern for God's people in every age and every nation. "Don't just taste God's word. Consume it. Inwardly digest it and make it your own. Then, declare God's victory through Jesus Christ to the nations regardless of the cost. Yes, the book and its mission may be sour in the stomach, but this will not last and the troubles of this age will give way to a glorious new creation."

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